

WP3: T3.5

Pedagogical Handbook for Domestic Violence Trainers

Training First-Line Professionals in the Police,
Justice, Medical and Social Sectors

Improving Access to Services for Victims of Domestic Violence
by Accelerating Change in Frontline Responder Organisations

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List of Abbreviations

DV	Domestic Violence
IMPROVE	Improving Access to Services for Victims of Domestic Violence by Accelerating Change in Frontline Responder Organisations
ASKABI	Asociación Askabide Liberación
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
DHPol	Deutsche Hochschule der Polizei
FORESEE	Foresee Kutatocsoport Nonprofit Kozhasznu Kft
MAI-PSP	Ministério da Administração Interna (PSP/ISCPSI)
MININT	Ministry of the Interior
PLV	Policia Local de Valencia
POLAMK	Poliisiammattikorkeakoulu
SIG	S.I.G.N.A.L. e.V. – Intervention im Gesundheitsbereich gegen Häusliche und Sexualisierte Gewalt
THL	Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos
UDEUSTO	Universidad De La Iglesia De Deusto Entidad Religiosa
VICESSE	Vienna Centre For Societal Security – Vicesse, Wiener Zentrum für Sozialwissenschaftliche Sicherheitsforschung
WWU	(Westfälische Wilhelms-) Universität Münster

Preface

Previous research revealed that in some countries topics such as preventing, detecting, and intervening domestic violence have so far been offered only seldom in trainings, the evaluation of such trainings even less. However, well-reflected knowledge in this context is particularly relevant for professionals who come into contact with victims of domestic violence. The purpose of this training handbook is therefore to support trainers in the fields of law enforcement, healthcare, social work, and justice sector on how to use these practice-oriented, science-based and evaluated training materials that can be found on the [IMPROVE training platform on domestic violence](#).

This platform is a resource for trainers who teach domestic violence. It is tailored to their needs to complement their trainings or to evaluate knowledge following training sessions using the materials and tools of the [IMPROVE training platform on domestic violence](#). Trainers have the flexibility to choose from a diverse range of materials within each module, with some content being mandatory to ensure a shared foundational understanding. **Except for two clearly designated self-learning modules, the platform is not intended to be a standalone self-study tool for learners.**

This handbook serves as a **pedagogic guide and** explains across seven chapters how the information, training materials and tools provided by the IMPROVE training platform on domestic violence can be used by trainers. **For those new to training, participation in a Train-the-Trainer course is nonetheless highly recommended.**

It is my pleasure as WP3 lead of IMPROVE to share this **pedagogic** handbook with you now.

Sincerely yours,

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Bettina Pfeleiderer". The signature is written in a cursive style with a long horizontal stroke extending to the right.

Prof. Bettina Pfeleiderer PhD MD
University of Münster, Germany

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Great strides have been made in Europe over the last decade in terms of preventing, detecting and intervening in cases of domestic violence. Several European Union member states have introduced measures and legislation to address this issue. Nevertheless, domestic violence remains one of the biggest challenges the European society is facing. Professionals who encounter domestic violence include frontline responders from law enforcement, healthcare, social work and the justice sector. However, they often lack the knowledge and confidence on how to respond to and how to recognise domestic violence, to understand its impact or to respond adequately in such situations and to provide needs-based support.

The provision of better support for domestic violence victims is of pressing need. This can be achieved by providing tailored advocacy measures alongside **ongoing training for professionals**. The [EU IMPROVE project](#) (*Improving Access to Services for Victims of Domestic Violence by Accelerating Change in Frontline Responder Organisations*) closed training gaps by developing new training materials and tool boxes for the [IMPROVE training platform on domestic violence](#).

Providing information in this handbook on how to train first line responders in domestic violence is another key contribution of the project — created through the collaboration of our partners from Austria, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Spain and Portugal. The handbook builds upon the training materials developed in the EU project [IMPRODOVA](#) (Improving Frontline Responses to High Impact Domestic Violence), further developing it through additional research conducted by the IMPROVE consortium. The IMPROVE partners (ASKABI, CNRS, DHPol, FORESEE, MAI-PSP, MININT, PLV, POLAMK, SIG, THL, UDEUSTO, VICESSE, WWU) translated the training materials, adapting the content to the Finnish, French, German, Austrian, Hungarian, Portuguese and Spanish national context. Additionally, partners tested and evaluated the materials in training sessions in all seven partner countries. Based on these results, the training materials underwent further revision – first in English, then across all seven project languages (see [D3.3](#)).

1.2 What can you find in the handbook?

In this handbook, trainers can find a summary of available training contents on the [IMPROVE training platform on domestic violence](#). In addition to the knowledge required to set up training courses using IMPROVE material, **this handbook also highlights the important soft skills that are essential to apply when training various stakeholder groups in the context of domestic violence**. These skills include the ability to listen, to provide constructive feedback, to take into account the potential biases and traumas of the participants in the training course, to communicate with intercultural competence, to acknowledge and be sensitive of possible stereotypes, to engage in a reflected way as well as to be aware of one's own biases and traumas, in order to prepare for the training course in the best possible way, taking care of both the participants and oneself.

2. Training Framework

2.1 General overview on the IMPROVE Training Platform

The [IMPROVE training platform](#) has a **modular, sector-specific structure** meaning that it is divided into different modules and sections, covering different aspects of domestic violence

and taking into account the specific needs of different target groups in different countries. The content and materials of the training modules can be combined in countless ways.

The general objectives of the IMPROVE training platform are:

- ✓ To provide trainers an overview of relevant topics on domestic violence.
- ✓ To provide trainers information on available national support services.
- ✓ To provide trainers awareness raising training material for students, practitioners, and managers.
- ✓ To provide trainers measures to enhance professional response to domestic violence.
- ✓ To provide trainers with stakeholder-tailored teaching methods and exercises.
- ✓ To provide trainers with the necessary information on how to conduct trainings using IMPROVE tools and materials.

The [IMPROVE training platform](#) has a **modular, sector-specific structure** meaning that it is divided into different modules and sections, covering different aspects of domestic violence and taking into account the specific needs of different target groups in different countries. The content and materials of the training modules can be combined in countless ways.

In this [chapter 2](#), we will first of all address the **key aspects of training facilitation to illustrate how trainers can design effective trainings in the specific context of domestic violence**. We cover the role of trainers, possible target groups, training objectives, and various factors that influence the duration of trainings.

Alongside, **we provide a brief excursus on ‘train-the-trainers’ for those new to facilitating trainings** ([see 2.1.1](#)). It offers context for the following far more specific guidance on addressing key factors in domestic violence training. These additional notes are **no substitute for a formal train-the-trainer course**, which we strongly recommend to ensure high-quality, interactive, and audience-specific sessions.

2.1.1 In a nutshell: general brief input for trainers (Train-the-Trainer)

Safe and supportive learning environment:

Establish a setting where participants can express feelings, doubts, or frustrations without fear of judgment or reprisal. Such an environment enables participants to process emotions and gain knowledge and skills that support desired attitude and behaviour changes, which is especially relevant in sensitive training context, such as domestic violence. [Appendix 7.1](#) summarises the key elements on how to **support creating and maintaining a safe learning environment**. These rules can be set in advance by the trainer or agreed upon with participants at the start. Confidentiality (“what is said here, stays here”) is essential and non-negotiable. It can also be useful to agree **on signalling when breaks are needed**, underlining that learning processes require time and space to be effective. Other useful rules include respecting diverse perspectives, avoiding judgmental language, and allowing everyone the choice to speak or remain silent when it feels appropriate

The role of the trainer

Trainers shall use their expertise and teaching skills to guide learning, embodying the positive behaviour they wish to convey ([see chapter 2.2](#)).

Facilitating effective trainings

Successful facilitation requires a combination of communication skills, knowledge of training methods and understanding which methods to choose for specific **objectives** (see [Appendix 7.2](#) for more information), **target groups** ([see chapter 2.3](#)) as well as a high competence in time management to monitor the process effectively. When working in a trainer tandem, practice effective co-facilitation by planning handoffs, modelling collaboration, and providing mutual support during challenging group dynamics

Training formats

Training formats **refer to the different ways in which training content can be delivered or experienced**. Trainings, workshops, seminars and lectures are the most commonly used formats. Their characteristics, requirements and examples are presented in **Table 4**.

All formats can be offered on an introductory level, to provide knowledge on a thematic complex or even to focus on (highly) specific aspects. These formats can additionally vary depending on the composition of the group (homogenous versus heterogenous and the learning environment (offline, online, hybrid and have all their advantages and disadvantages. See Table 5 for an overview of the advantages and disadvantages).

Requirements for the implementation of the training

The successful implementation of trainings depend on various factors related to participants, content, time management, and resources, so please adjust the format accordingly:

- **Target group:** Training content and methods must be tailored to participants’ professional background (e.g., study phase, position), learning and working habits, work description and responsibilities, role understanding, prior knowledge, motivations, expectations, interests, and values. Terminology should be adjusted to match the group’s familiar language, especially if participants come from specific organisations or settings (see more information in [chapter 2.3](#) on target groups).
- **Group composition:** Training can be conducted at an institutional level with participants from the same or different organisations, either internally or externally, and in homogeneous or heterogeneous groups, each with advantages and disadvantages (see also [chapter 2.4](#), **Table 2**). **Multi-professional groups can facilitate knowledge**

transfer and improve cooperation, but they require more time and exchange due to varying conceptions and definitions of domestic violence, differing levels of knowledge, and the diverse roles and limitations participants have within their professions, of which other trainees are often not fully aware. For trainers, it is essential to establish a common ground and shared understanding, and to address potentially challenging group dynamics. Homogeneous groups are easier for trainers to manage, but attention must be paid to ensure all participants feel safe to engage. When participants come from different hierarchical levels, practical experience or levels of education, the trainer must encourage all participants to share their experiences and thoughts equally, avoiding judgment or dominance. Positive encouragement can also be beneficial to train interdisciplinary groups to broaden their understanding of different perspectives and areas of responsibility.

- **Time schedule: Time planning must consider group size (best is a group size < 15)** and background to allocate sufficient time for discussions and activities. Alternating receptive (inputs) and active (group discussions, individual and group exercises) phases promote engagement and understanding ([see chapter 2.5](#)). **Formats can differ regarding to the allocation of the training time** (one single training versus multiple trainings days with or without intervals in between). If training sessions stretch out over a longer period, it is advisable to allow enough time for participants to recap and share their experiences at the beginning of a subsequent training day. You may also use the time between sessions to support the transfer of learning into practice. This can include reflective tasks, sharing new experiences with an accountability partner at set intervals, or group discussions via learning platforms such as Moodle.
- **Instructions and transparency:** Participants should be clearly informed about the agenda, objectives, and relevance of the training content before and during training. Written instructions for exercises support smooth participation.

Training equipment and materials

Appropriate spatial and media equipment is essential for a comfortable and effective learning environment. Trainers generally need:

- Training plan with objectives, content, and schedule
- Participant list
- Handouts with written instructions for exercises and reflections
- Factsheets adapted to participants' educational and professional backgrounds; these should be actively used during training
- PowerPoint slides for each module, adaptable as needed
- Flipchart, pens, and other materials as required
- Presentation essentials: laptop, projector, screen, and external speakers if necessary
- Questionnaires or feedback forms (see Appendices [7.4.1](#), [7.4.2](#), [7.4.3](#))

Evaluation

It is of importance to **evaluate whether the training is meeting its objectives** and that it is having a positive impact on the participants. Feedback from the participants should be incorporated into future training sessions to continuously improve the quality and effectiveness of the training (see [chapter 5](#) and [Appendix 7.4](#) for a questionnaire that can be used for training evaluations).

Contracted work

If the training has been requested by an organisation, the training should be designed in close cooperation between the organisation and the trainer

Checklist: A DV training preparation checklist can be found in [Appendix 7.5](#)

2.2 Role of trainers

The main objective of trainers is to teach managers, practitioners, students, and other trainers to recognise and respond adequately to domestic violence to provide the best possible support for victims.

To support those being trained well, trainers should:

- ✓ **tailor the training to the target group**, considering their prior knowledge, needs, specific roles, job description and responsibilities in the context of domestic violence, the training group size, training duration, learning habits and preferences when developing a methodologically diverse training concept.
- ✓ **create a safe learning environment**, especially given the sensitivity of domestic violence related topics; trainers should know how to deal with participants who disclose their own experience of domestic violence.
- ✓ **model professional behaviour**, including respectful communication and emotional regulation.
- ✓ **facilitate learning** by guiding trainees through the training structure, key concepts, discussions and reflections.
- ✓ **be culturally sensitive** in their trainings
- ✓ **monitor group dynamics** and adjust methods as needed to support learning and safety.
- ✓ **foster dialogue and exchange** between participants.
- ✓ **Promote empathy** and trauma-informed understanding in discussions and exercises.
- ✓ **encourage self-awareness** and critical reflection, for example on bias, stereotypes, professional attitudes, self-care, and the professional error culture.
- ✓ **introduce and discuss tools**, methods, and frameworks for improving domestic violence response.
- ✓ **support practical skill-building**, such as case assessment, communication, and referral.
- ✓ **evaluate the training** to secure its quality.
- ✓ **ensure effective training**, it is advisable to involve a trainer tandem with expertise in the relevant sector and on violence protection (preferably with psychological training

2.3 Target groups

The training material addresses trainers providing trainings for students and practitioners from various professional backgrounds, including the **police sector**, **health sector** (e.g., physicians, nurses, midwives, dentists, psychologists and psychiatrists), the **social sector**, including the **educational sector** (e.g., family and childcare professionals, mediators, teachers and (school) social workers) and the **justice sector** (e.g., prosecutors and judges). Further, the training material is suitable for training other professional groups who regularly come into contact with victims of domestic violence, be it in the phase of identifying, assessing, and responding to domestic violence cases, particularly vulnerable and underserved victims to access support services of domestic violence.

To ensure effective training, it is advisable to involve a trainer tandem with expertise in the relevant sector and on violence protection (preferably with psychological training).

It is crucial to have a thorough understanding of the participants' professional backgrounds and tasks to tailor the training to the specific target group, ensuring a comprehensive and well-founded approach. **The target groups that the IMPROVE training material** has been designed for are described in more detail in **Table 1**, while the **objectives** that can be addressed with these target groups are listed in **Table 2**.

Most of the exercises and information provided on the training platform are designed for participants with a higher formal education. Therefore, trainers may need to adapt the training content to their specific target group in terms of terminology and language.

*Table 1: Description of target groups which should be trained by IMPROVE training materials. * The list is not exhaustive.*

Category	Target Groups*	Relevance of Training
Managers	<p>Police sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heads of investigation, preventive policing, or emergency response units (e.g., inspectors, superintendents, sergeants) <p>Health sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical administrative services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure effective implementation of domestic violence related policies and procedures • Oversee training programs • Ensure adequate staffing and resources • Promote a culture of accountability and support for frontline responders
Practitioners	<p>Police sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Police officers <p>Healthcare:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physicians • Nurses • Midwives • Dentists • Psychiatrists, psychologists and psychotherapists • Pharmacists <p>Social/ education sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family and childcare professionals • Mediators • Teachers • E.g. (School) social workers <p>Justice sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prosecutors • Lawyers • Judges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Often first point of contact for victims • Interact with victims in hospitals, shelters, counselling centres, community organisations and many have an intrinsic motivation to do a good job.
Students	<p>Police sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Police students <p>Health sector: e.g.</p>	Next generation of professionals who will deal with domestic violence

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medical students • Dental students • Pharmacy students • Midwifery and nursing students <p>Social /education sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social work students • Teachers <p>Justice sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Law students 	
Trainers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interested persons from related fields • Ideally have practical experience in relevant sector or violence protection training 	Train-the-trainer programme: They will have experience and expertise to train managers, practitioners, students, and trainers

2.4 Specific objectives of domestic violence training

This section outlines the most important objectives of domestic violence training, structured by the target groups that can be addressed with the material of the IMPROVE training platform. This section also highlights the key role of trainers and the tasks they must fulfil to ensure these objectives are met. Successful facilitation requires a combination of communication skills, knowledge of domestic violence and training methods and, in certain cases, formal trainer training.

Table 2: Description of Objectives of the Training stratified by target group.

** The list is not exhaustive.*

Category	Objectives of the Training*
Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge about the extent and effects of domestic violence • Knowledge about the strategies for intervening in domestic violence (best practice models) • Knowledge on the important prerequisites for a successful intervention: • Knowledge on trauma-informed and victim-centred approach • Knowledge on efficient cross-sector cooperation • Knowledge on evaluation of intervention measures <p>Knowledge on support and training for professionals</p>
Practitioners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of signs and symptoms of domestic violence • Knowledge on how to respond effectively and sensitively • Knowledge of support systems, the importance of referrals and safety measures • Knowledge of legal/ethical issues (e.g., reporting, confidentiality, protection acts, legally compliant documentation)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of evidence-based cross-sector collaboration • Knowledge of the importance of reflection and self-care
Students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be aware of domestic violence in contrast to healthy relationships • Understand its impact on individuals, families, communities • Know what could be done to recognise, respond to, and prevent domestic violence
Trainers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness and educate about domestic violence • Know about dynamics, signs and symptoms • Understand scope and impact • Know about trauma-informed, victim-centred approach • Know how to address domestic violence effectively • Know about best practices, cross-sector collaboration and innovation • Know about training materials and exercises • Know how to deal with affected participants • Know how to monitor and to evaluate trainings.

Trainers play a key role in ensuring that objectives are met:

- ✓ **Raise** awareness and educate.
- ✓ **Provide opportunities** to share professional experiences of domestic violence.
- ✓ **Promote** a trauma-informed, victim-centred approach.
- ✓ **Monitor and evaluate** effectiveness.
- ✓ **Promote best practices** and innovation.
- ✓ **Introduce how to work collaboratively** and coordinate efforts with other professionals. and community stakeholders, such as police officers, health professionals, social workers, and legal professionals, to address domestic violence effectively.
- ✓ **Clarify** that first line responders ~~are and~~ cannot be expected to respond to all aspects related to the cases of violence on their own; intersectoral cooperation is the key.
- ✓ **Improve consistency** and high quality of training interventions.

To reach the following specific objectives, the tasks of the trainers will be described accordingly.

Understanding the dynamics of domestic violence

- ✓ To introduce the definitions and forms of domestic violence.
- ✓ To provide information on the dynamics, including risk and protective factors of domestic violence.

Recognising the signs and symptoms of domestic violence

- ✓ To present the signs and consequences of domestic violence, including physical, emotional, and psychological abuse.

Understanding the impact of domestic violence

- ✓ To share the potential short-term and long-term physical and psychological effects of domestic violence on victims, their children, and the family system.

Responding to domestic violence

- ✓ To provide information on how to respond to a disclosure of domestic violence in a sensitive and empathetic manner, while also adhering to ethical and legal guidelines.
- ✓ To foster the skills and thus increase the trainees' confidence to identify domestic violence or to respond to cases of domestic violence.

Providing support and referrals

- ✓ To introduce possible support services to help victims of domestic violence.
- ✓ To raise awareness about the trainees' responsibilities, tasks, opportunities, and limitations.
- ✓ To provide information on how to deal with difficult situations, the relevance of trauma-informed care, and the importance of self-care.

Preventing future incidents

- ✓ To present strategies for prevention, such as early intervention, education, and advocacy, including risk assessment, safety planning, counselling, legal and financial assistance, and other relevant resources.

Fostering diversity competence

- ✓ To share information on how to work with victims of domestic violence from diverse backgrounds and cultures, recognising and respecting their unique experiences and perspectives.

2.5 Duration of training

The training material of the [IMPROVE training platform on domestic violence](#) consists of ten modules. This content can be flexibly adapted: Trainers can decide whether to make use of the complete content of a module or only of selected parts, adjust the training duration by choosing specific modules, topics, or exercises, as well as the sequence in which they are delivered.

The group size, among other factors, influences the duration of trainings. Experience has shown that training on domestic violence should ideally be conducted in groups of 10 to 16 participants (Juszczuk, Sondern & Pfeleiderer 2022)¹. The literature research and experiences from other training courses suggest that trainings on domestic violence for professionals should ideally have a duration of two days (Juszczuk, Sondern & Pfeleiderer 2022). **It can be assumed that these two days are not feasible in their full length in many settings. Thus, it is possible to offer the**

¹ Juszczuk, P., Sondern, L., & Pfeleiderer, B. (2022). Introduction and evaluation of a clinical compulsory elective course on domestic violence. *GMS Journal for Medical Education*, 39(5):Doc56. <https://doi.org/10.3205/zma001577>

training as a split two-day course over a longer period of time, in split half-day or even shorter trainings, depending on the needs and the availability of the trainees. The recommended minimum duration of the training is two hours. **In this case, the training's outcome is mainly to raise awareness.**

3. Structure of the training platform

3.1 General overview

The [IMPROVE training platform on domestic violence](#) is available **online** and has a separate link for direct access: www.training.improve-horizon.eu. No registration is necessary and there are no costs when using the training platform.

The training platform is composed in the following way:

Training modules: The training content is structured in ten detailed modules dealing with different aspects of domestic violence. At the beginning of each module, an overview with hyperlinked subchapters provides easy navigation, followed by the specification of the target group.

Module introductions: The introductions of the modules provide a concise overview of the module with hyperlinks to its most important aspects.

Module objectives: Each module's introduction is followed by the respective objectives. These objectives help trainers to focus on the key messages from the training and to clarify what they want to achieve through each training session and exercise.

Module content: In the main part, every module offers well-structured continuous text that integrates diverse training materials.

Training materials:

- **Training materials related to the modules:** Each of the ten detailed training modules contains a variety of material and didactic tools, such as (interactive) graphics, flow diagrams, (interactive) case scenarios, videos, quizzes, tables and factsheets. These tools have been designed in accordance with the key themes covered in each module of the training platform. Their aim is to create opportunities for interactive learning (**see Table 3**). This material can be downloaded from the modules, but it is also provided in a clear format stripped of any surrounding text in the separate training material sections. The training tools are sector specific: [police](#), [medical sector](#), [social sector](#), [legal sector](#).
- **Repository of training materials:** Each repository is sector specific ([police](#), [medical sector](#), [social sector](#), [legal sector](#); **see Table 3**). You can find **exemplary presentations for 45- or 90-minute sessions**, as well as the material from the [Appendices](#) of this handbook, which you can download and adapt to your needs. Every sector has its own repository, but they have all the same structure:
 - *Collection of training concepts, slides and additional material for trainers:*
 - Training concepts and workshops
 - Slide collections
 - Supportive material for trainers (the same for all sectors)
 - Surveys for evaluation of trainings (the same for all sectors)
 - *Depending on the sector, further additional material may be available.*

The following modules are offered on training platform:

- Module 1: Forms and dynamics of domestic violence
- Module 2: Indicators of domestic violence
- Module 3: Communication in cases of domestic violence
- Module 4 (Police): Police investigation and legal proceedings
- Module 4 (Health sector): Medical assessment and securing of evidence
- Module 4 (Social sector): Support services of the social sector
- Module 4 (Legal sector): Judicial investigation and protection of victims
- Module 5: Risk assessment and safety planning
- Module 6: International standards and legal frameworks in Europe
- Module 7: Principles of interorganisational cooperation in cases of domestic violence
- Module 8: Stereotypes and unconscious bias
- Module 9: Self-care
- Module 10: Line managers in cases of domestic violence

Table 3 shows the list of all ten hyperlinked modules for the various professional sectors, as well as the sections with the training materials.

All modules are interconnected with cross-references. There are also hyperlinks within the modules to support easy navigation and deeper exploration of specific topics. **The modular structure of the training platform enables trainers to select specific objectives for a training,** using either the respective parts of different modules or an individual module. In this way, the training can be adapted to the knowledge or skill gaps and needs of different target groups, such as e.g., police officers, general practitioners, and teachers. In addition, **the trainers can adapt the content and exercises from the modules to their own training style and needs.**

Table 3: Sector and available modules with links

Sector	Available modules with links
Police sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Module 1: Forms and dynamics of domestic violence • Module 2: Indicators of domestic violence • Module 3: Communication in cases of domestic violence • Module 4: Police investigation and legal proceedings • Module 5: Risk assessment and safety planning • Module 6: International standards and legal frameworks in Europe • Module 7: Principles of inter-organisational cooperation in cases of domestic violence • Module 8: Stereotypes and unconscious bias • Module 9: Self-care • Module 10: Line managers in cases of domestic violence • Data and statistics • Training materials of the modules • Repository of training materials
Health sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Module 1: Forms and dynamics of domestic violence

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Module 2: Indicators of domestic violence • Module 3: Communication in cases of domestic violence • Module 4: Medical assessment and securing of evidence • Module 5: Risk assessment and safety planning • Module 6: International standards and legal frameworks in Europe • Module 7: Principles of inter-organisational cooperation in cases of domestic violence • Module 8: Stereotypes and unconscious bias • Module 9: Self-care • Module 10: Line managers in cases of domestic violence • Data and statistics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials of the modules • Repository of training materials
Social sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Module 1: Forms and dynamics of domestic violence • Module 2: Indicators of domestic violence • Module 3: Communication in cases of domestic violence • Module 4: Support services of the social sector • Module 5: Risk assessment and safety planning • Module 6: International standards and legal frameworks in Europe • Module 7: Principles of inter-organisational cooperation in cases of domestic violence • Module 8: Stereotypes and unconscious bias • Module 9: Self-care • Module 10: Line managers in cases of domestic violence • Data and statistics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials of the modules • Repository of training materials
Legal sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Module 1: Forms and dynamics of domestic violence • Module 2: Indicators of domestic violence • Module 3: Communication in cases of domestic violence • Module 4: Access to justice • Module 5: Risk assessment and safety planning • Module 6: International standards and legal frameworks in Europe • Module 7: Principles of inter-organisational cooperation in cases of domestic violence • Module 8: Stereotypes and unconscious bias • Module 9: Self-care • Module 10: Line managers in cases of domestic violence • Data and statistics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials of the modules • Repository of training materials

3.2 Targeting specific skills, capacities, competencies

The training materials are tailored to the professionals' knowledge, attitudes (including motivation and values) and behaviours (including skills, capacities and competencies). This is clearly foreseen in the training concepts well as in the overall concept of the IMPROVE training platform.

Knowledge:

- Fostering the understanding of the dynamics of domestic violence, including the various forms it can take (physical, psychological, sexual, financial, etc.). → [Module 1 \(police, medical sector, social sector, legal sector\)](#)
- Enhancing knowledge of the legal framework and rights of victims, as well as the obligations of professionals in reporting and addressing domestic violence. → [Module 6 \(police, medical sector, social sector, legal sector\)](#)
- Raising awareness of the available support systems and resources for victims, including shelters, counselling services, and legal aid. → [Module 4 \(police, medical sector, social sector, legal sector\)](#)

Attitudes:

- Promoting empathy and sensitivity towards victims, recognising the psychological impact of domestic violence. → [Module 3 \(police, medical sector, social sector, legal sector\)](#)
- Challenging stereotypes and misconceptions about domestic violence, such as victim-blaming attitudes. → [Module 8 \(police, medical sector, social sector, legal sector\)](#)
- Encouraging a victim-centred approach that prioritises the safety and well-being of the victim (all modules), but also the well-being of frontline responders and practitioners (self-care) when working with victims of domestic violence. → [Module 9 \(police, medical sector, social sector, legal sector\)](#)

Behaviours:

- Developing practical skills for identifying and responding to signs of domestic violence → [Module 2 \(police, medical sector, social sector, legal sector\)](#)
- and assessing the risk. → [Module 5 \(police, medical sector, social sector, legal sector\)](#)
- Improving communication skills to interact with victims (feel heard and supported). → [Module 3 \(police, medical sector, social sector, legal sector\)](#)
- Implementing best practices for evidence collection/documentation in cases of domestic violence. → [Module 4 \(police, medical sector, social sector, legal sector\)](#)
- Strengthening inter-agency cooperation. → [Module 7 \(police, medical sector, social sector, legal sector\)](#), [Module 10 \(police, medical sector, social sector, legal sector\)](#)

4. Methodological approaches

The training platform includes different didactic approaches, from theoretical explanations to practice-oriented exercises. The aim is to enable interactive learning. During the training development, great effort was made to include as much information as possible. However, at the European level, it was not always possible to provide appropriate additional material for the specific national contexts to accompany the comprehensive text content. **When trainers work with the national version of their training context, they are encouraged to provide**

additional information and material relevant to the respective target group and the regional/ national setting.

Most modules are structured in such a way that the input is presented at the beginning, followed by opportunities for reflection and discussion. The inclusion of the trainees' experiences and perceptions, especially regarding the case studies, facilitates creating an interactive learning atmosphere.

4.1 Domestic violence as a teaching topic

Domestic violence can be a difficult topic to teach because it is a sensitive and emotionally charged topic. Thus, different situations, topics or group dynamics can influence the quality of the training and the wellbeing of the participants. Some of these influencing factors and ideas for dealing with such situations are listed below.

Safe and supportive learning environment

To create a safe and supportive learning environment is one of the most important tasks and challenges in group work, and it is an important requirement for a training on domestic violence. Empathy, openness, and the ability to share experiences are important social skills to foster. Participants should be encouraged to express their opinions openly and participate in group exercises. The trainer's role is to facilitate interaction between participants to achieve goals and create a constructive environment. Effective group work includes everyone engaging actively. Additionally, good communication skills are needed, such as active listening, asking clarifying questions, using I-statements, making meaningful contributions, respecting others' opinions, and providing polite answers. [Appendix 7.1](#) summarises how a safe training environment can be ensured.

Participants as victims, witnesses, or perpetrators of violence

For trainers, it is important to remember that some of the participants may themselves be victims, witnesses, or perpetrators of domestic violence. For such participants, some of the topics discussed in the training might be particularly difficult, and it is therefore essential for trainers to be prepared for such situations. In any case, the language used should be respectful and non-pejorative. However, a clear stance against violence must be taken.

As a golden rule, a disturbance of the learning process should be attended. At the beginning of a training session, it is important to address the fact that domestic violence is a sensitive issue that could affect anyone. You could suggest that they can always contact you privately after and/or in breaks in the class or leave the course without further explanation. A support strategy in such cases could be to invite the participants to talk about their experiences of violence and their emotional situation in private. The conversation can take place before the training session, during the break or after the end of the training session. The trainer should discuss with the respective participant whether they prefer to continue, pause or leave the training, considering the given circumstances.

Teaching about domestic violence can also provoke fear or resistance in trainees, which may be expressed as criticism or other expressions of disapproval during the course. In this case, a possible strategy could be to summarise the exercise again, to highlight the main points of the discussion again, to ask the group for their opinion, or to remind the whole group/respective participant of the group rules. It can also help to acknowledge the resistance

and comment on it in a friendly manner. If it does not stop, you should seek a conversation during a break.

Stereotypes and unconscious biases in the context of domestic violence

The training content is designed to encourage and challenge participants to think and talk about domestic violence. Central topics in this context concern the participants' perception of violence as well as their attitudes towards it. **In the context of domestic violence, stereotypes and biases can play a significant role in shaping how individuals perceive victims and perpetrators of domestic violence, and how they respond to incidents of violence.**

Stereotypes and unconscious biases in the context of domestic violence may include:

- To blame the victim for the violence, question whether the victim caused violence through their own behaviour or to ask why the victim did not simply leave the violent situation.
- To assume that men or elderly cannot be victims of domestic violence, or that certain cultural or religious groups condone or even encourage domestic violence.
- To not believe a victim because he or she has a disability or impairment.
- To expect that domestic violence is caused by exceptional situations as alcohol abuse or jealousy.
- To assume that perpetrators are always aggressive and rude, when, in reality, they can seem nice and kind.
- To focus on the punishment of the perpetrator, disregarding the needs and situation of the victim.
- To assume that separation/divorce alone is a safe solution for ending the violence.
- To believe that domestic violence does not occur in the context of their profession, in their environment or that dealing with it is not their responsibility.

These stereotypes and biases can have serious consequences for victims of domestic violence, as they may prevent them from seeking help or being taken seriously, and thus risk causing an escalation of the violence or even endanger their life. The self-learning training (→ [Module 8 \(police, medical sector, social sector, justice sector\)](#)) encourages trainers and participants to reflect on the stereotypes and biases possibly underlying their own perceptions, views, attitudes and reactions.

Professional secrecy and data protection

If you use your own cases, it must be clear that real names and the details of individual cases must be avoided. Any information revealed by the participants must not leave the training, as the topics are sensitive and require strict confidentiality.

4.2 Training requirements

The goal in the long run is that learning content is not only understood but also firmly anchored, internalised, will be remembered in a sustainable way, and so practicable that it is applicable in practice. Thus, the training content is designed to enable interactive work mainly in groups (**module, 1-7, 10**), but also in self-study (**module 8, 9**). Group formats ideally foster interactive and immersive learning experiences, in which participants can engage with each other, while self-learning modules enable the participants to work at their own pace and according to their own interests.

The accessibility of trainings is also an important factor: Webinars and hybrid learning environments can provide more accessible and convenient training options for those who cannot attend face-to-face events. **Beyond this, training platforms like the IMPROVE training platform can serve as cognitive maps for both, learners and trainers.** They enable self-directed learning at an individual pace, allowing participants to revisit topics and access resources as needed. **Simultaneously, trainers can use the platform to orient themselves, identify potential knowledge or understand gaps regarding specific aspects, and to explore a variety of didactic methods they might have overlooked.**

Simultaneously, trainers can use the platform to orient themselves, identify potential knowledge or understand gaps regarding specific aspects, and to explore a variety of didactic methods they might have overlooked.

When planning a training on domestic violence, several requirements need to be considered with regard to the content to ensure an effective and safe learning environment, and a tailored approach to meet the diverse needs of different target groups.

- **Accuracy:** The training should provide accurate and up-to-date information on the dynamics of domestic violence, including its various forms, its impact on victims and their children, as well as the legal and social services available to support them.
- **Sensitivity:** The training should be delivered in a (trauma-)sensitive and respectful manner. Stigmatising language should be avoided, and diverse backgrounds and cultures of those affected by domestic violence should be respected.
- **Applicability:** The training should be relevant and applicable to the specific context and needs of the participants, whether they are managers, practitioners or students.
- **Practicality:** The training should be practical and provide strategies for responding to incidents of domestic violence, including how to recognise the signs and symptoms, how to provide support and referrals, and how to develop safety plans for victims.
- **Evaluation:** The training should be evaluated regularly to ensure that it is meeting its objectives and that it is having a positive impact on the participants. Feedback from the participants should be incorporated into future training sessions to continuously improve the quality and effectiveness of the training.

4.3 Training formats and methods

Training formats refer to the different ways in which training content can be delivered or experienced. Trainers can choose from various formats to best support participants to access the content, explore the topic, understand key points, and develop their own responses. Most often used in the context of providing knowledge in domestic violence are trainings, workshops, seminars and lectures (see *Table 4 below for an overview of the main characteristics of these formats, examples and requirements*). [In Appendix 7.2](#) the **advantages, applications and requirements of the various training methods** that can be used for domestic violence trainings are summarised.

Training formats should be consistent with one's own training style, the needs of the participants and the objectives of the training, for example, to develop certain attitudes, competences, knowledge, and skills.

For all training formats should be defined first:

- What topics do you want to cover?
- How much time do you have?
- What do you expect the participants to learn?

Table 4: Typical trainings formats, presented with their main characteristics, examples and their requirements.

Training format	Example	Requirement
<p>Trainings</p> <p>A structured, hands-on learning process designed to alter behaviour and improve specific skills.</p>	<p>A training session on trauma-informed care for practitioners, teaching and practicing with them specific techniques to interact with survivors of domestic violence.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires training to facilitate trainings, especially knowledge of a variety of methods • Requires knowledge of the practical world of the participants as well as of the theoretical framework of the training content
<p>Workshops</p> <p>A collaborative session where a moderator guides a group to collectively develop a solution or approach to a problem.</p>	<p>A workshop for students to create a community outreach plan for domestic violence awareness.</p> <p>A multiprofessional workshop for practitioners to establish a common ground for cooperation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires training to moderate group processes and to present the outcomes • Requires knowledge of the framework/background of the specific context for which a solution shall be elaborated
<p>Seminars</p> <p>A more formal, instructor-led format, using various interactive methods, to achieve learning goals, often checked through a final assessment.</p>	<p>A seminar on the psychological impact of domestic violence, providing and discussing an overview of research findings.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires scientific knowledge, didactic qualification and ideally practical insights.
<p>Lectures</p> <p>A formal learning method where an expert delivers a presentation to a large group, primarily to provide foundational knowledge and background information.</p>	<p>A lecture on the legal frameworks of domestic violence intervention, including case studies and debates.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires high expertise on the topic • Requires an inspiring speaker and ideally visuals supporting the attention of the learners • Requires didactic knowledge with regards to activating

		methods for large groups
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Table 5 describes different training formats with their advantages and disadvantages to help participants gain new information, reflect on attitudes and practise skills.

Table 5: Trainings formats with their advantages (pros) and disadvantages (cons).

Training format	Pros	Cons
Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly interactive and participatory • Fosters new/practical solutions to specific problems • Enhances collaboration • Creates group ownership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May lack a deep dive into theoretical knowledge • Outcomes can vary based on group dynamics
Seminars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Characterized by structured and organised learning • Broad range of interactive didactic methods applicable • Provides a good theoretical foundation • Fosters understanding and empathy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants may have varying levels of engagement • Can be less focused on immediate, practical application
Lectures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to organise • Cost-effective for large groups • Efficient way to deliver a large amount of information/ a strong theoretical foundation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficult to tailor to individual learning needs • Low interaction may reduce reflection on the content • Moreover, passive learning may reduce motivation and the learning curve • Less focus on immediate, practical application
Variations of training format		
Online formats (training, workshop, seminar, lecture)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More limited interaction and exchange • Challenges to assess understanding • Possible technical disturbances

Online based self-learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility • Learn at own pace • Easily updated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No interaction • No exchange • Challenges to assess understanding
Multi-professional formats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Widen the perspective • Foster tolerance, empathy, and communication skills • Enhance collaboration • Provide practical experience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires coordination with multiple professions • May slow down progress, as a common (e. g. problem-solving and knowledge) base must first be established
Specialised training formats (e.g., trauma informed care, forensic evidence collection, cultural competence)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focuses on specialised content • Enhances sensitivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May require (significant) training on the side of the facilitator of the format

4.4 Training materials and didactic tools

Training materials is the digital content provided for training, such as handouts, videos, visuals or quizzes. They are primarily intended for conveying information or providing practice, while **didactic tools** are primarily the methods that actively support and promote the learning process. These can include interactive elements such as reflection exercises or case studies.

A variety of training materials and didactic tools can be utilised to enhance an activating learning experience:

- **Visuals:** Visuals can be used, e.g., in the form of posters or PowerPoint slides. These can illustrate the learning content, stimulate the discussion and thus facilitate to remember what was learnt and discussed. They can be also helpful for participants who want to take notes. The drafting of structured cards detailing how to act in certain situations. Examples include the [VIPROM Med.Doc.Card®](#) and [Dent.Doc.Card®](#), which provide guidance on how to document injuries for use in court.
- **Handouts:** Based on the information on the training platform, downloadable sector-specific factsheets were designed for every module. These can serve as handouts in a course or workshop.
- **Case studies:** Case studies **have been prepared for most modules to make the topic more tangible through concrete examples, enable a more practice-oriented discussion of possible interventions**, and encourage participants to critically examine different perspectives and decision-making processes. They foster knowledge exchange, critical thinking and will enhance teaching by analysis of realistic scenarios.

They require however moderation and some may hesitate to share personal experiences with the topic of domestic violence.

- **Simulated Patient scenarios**: This employs **professionally trained actors to realistically portray victims of domestic violence, helping medical students and professionals recognise both emotional and physical signs in a controlled, safe environment**. This method enhances trauma-sensitive communication by allowing learners to practice empathetic interactions without fear of judgment. Overall, integrating simulated patients into medical curricula empowers students to develop both clinical and interpersonal skills essential for effectively identifying and supporting victims of domestic violence.
- **Videos**: Videos **can be used to illustrate different scenarios and provide examples of how to handle situations**. In addition to videos which can be found online, also training videos, which are about 1-2 minutes in length and summarise the most important aspects of each module have been developed and can be found on the training platform. The used drawn figures were diversified by a graphic designer to include further gender and diversity aspects.
- **Questions for reflections can be found after each video** and provide a deeper understanding of the topic. This self-reflection encourages long-term changes. However, it requires self-motivation and is time-consuming.
- **Quizzes**: Quizzes can be used by participants after a training to test their knowledge.

All training materials and didactic tools can be used in combination to provide a more comprehensive learning experience, but it is important to ensure that they meet the participants' needs. Additionally, materials should be accessible to all participants, taking into consideration any potential language or accessibility barriers.

4.5. Role plays

Role plays are a very useful didactic tool for activating participants in trainings on domestic violence and for developing practical skills

(e.g., communication with victims). However, the effectiveness of this tool depends on its preparation (e.g., it can also foster biases). To avoid negative outcomes, this handbook devotes an entire subchapter to role plays.

4.5.1 General guidelines

In the following subchapter, a general guidance is provided on how to use role plays in trainings on domestic violence and what needs to be considered. The [guidelines can also be downloaded here](#).

➤ **Psychological Safety & Trauma Awareness**

- **Role plays on domestic violence can be triggering** – for participants and observers alike.
- Inform participants that role plays can be traumatic and that **they can leave the role play if they suddenly feel it is affecting them too much**.
- Offer **content warnings** before each scenario.
- Work in a trainer-tandem.
- Have a **mental health professional or support resource** available, especially in longer or more intensive sessions.

➤ **Clear Learning Objectives per Sector**

In case of multisector trainings, each sector has a different role and perspective. Tailor scenarios so they:

- Reflect **realistic dilemmas** participants would face in practice.
- Highlight **intersections** (e.g., how medical records support prosecution, awareness-raising activities by social workers to enable police officers to better understand certain situations).
- Support **interdisciplinary collaboration**.

For example:

- **Police** → risk assessment, trauma-informed interviewing, evidence gathering.
- **Social workers** → identifying signs of abuse, safety planning, ensuring the victim's safety by liaising with emergency shelters.
- **Medical professionals** → documentation, recognizing physical/psychological symptoms, mandated reporting.
- **Justice sector** → legal protections, restraining orders, victim support during court processes.

➤ **Realism & Accuracy**

- Use **scenarios based on real cases** (anonymized).
- Reflect **different forms of abuse**:
 - Physical
 - Emotional/psychological
 - Financial
 - Coercive control
 - Technological abuse
- Include **cultural, gender, or immigration status complexity** where relevant.
- Involve **actors or trained facilitators** who can portray trauma responses accurately.

➤ **Role Clarity and Guidance**

- Provide **brief role descriptions** in writing (e.g., “You’re a survivor who doesn’t want the abuser arrested”; “You’re a paramedic who noticed signs of fear”).
- Clarify **boundaries**: what participants can and can’t do in character.
- Encourage empathy, **not just procedure**—you’re training responders to *see the person*, not just the problem.
- Provide time for participants to find into their roles
- Use a clear signal for the start of the role and the end
- Allow for time for the participants to disengage from their roles

➤ **Debriefing is Non-Negotiable**

- Hold structured **debriefs immediately after each role play**:
 - What went well?
 - What was hard?
 - What could have been done differently?
- Discuss both **technical actions** (e.g., did the police follow protocol? (if this role play was used in police training)) and **relational dynamics** (e.g., was the survivor treated with dignity?).
- Use debriefs to correct **myths**, challenge **biases**, and build **shared understanding**.

➤ **Interdisciplinary Insight**

- Use role play to highlight where communication breaks down between services.
- Let participants observe each other's methods (e.g., how police interviews differ from social worker conversations).
- Include moments of transferrals – these are often where victims of domestic violence fall through the cracks.

➤ **Structure and Facilitation**

- Keep role plays structured:
 - Introduction → Role play → Debrief
- Assign skilled facilitators to guide, stop, or re-direct as needed.
- Consider using “pause and reflect” techniques during intense scenarios.

➤ **Ethical Framing**

- Reinforce that this is not theatre; the goal is professional growth.
- Avoid sensationalism or over-dramatization.
- Use inclusive language (e.g., not all victims are women, and not all abusers are men, though gender dynamics do matter).

➤ **Optional: Recording or Observation**

- With consent, consider recording role plays for educational review.
- Or use observers who note behaviours, strengths, and missed opportunities during the scenario.

4.5.2 Example scenarios

Here are some ideas for example scenarios:

1. Emergency Room Encounter
 - Woman comes in with “accidental fall” injuries. Partner is hovering.
 - Medical staff must identify signs of domestic violence and coordinate with a social worker or the police.
2. Child Witness Involvement
 - Police respond to a call regarding domestic violence; a child has witnessed the violence.
 - Obligation to coordinate with the child protection services and to assess the risk.
3. Legal Barriers
 - Victim of domestic violence seeks restraining order but is hesitant to testify.
 - Role play explores justice worker and advocate support strategies.
4. Victim of domestic violence with an immigration background
 - The victim fears deportation if abuse is reported.
 - Social services, legal aid, and police must coordinate sensitively.

In [Appendix 7.3](#) an example for a role play scenario is presented: „**Between Protection and Fear**”. The **objective is to practice trauma-informed, collaborative** responses when a victim of domestic violence is hesitant to testify in a legal process, especially for obtaining a restraining order. Participants will explore professional responsibilities, survivor autonomy, and cross-sector support.

5. Evaluation of the training

Evaluations are useful methods to determine **the extent to which participants are satisfied with the content and didactic methods of the training, the learning environment, and measure the increase of knowledge, competencies**, perceived self-perceived confidence to act etc. They are essential for improving the quality of the training and provide important information in the long term. Evaluations can be carried out after individual work steps, e.g., at the end of a module or at the end of a day in the case of training over several days or at the end of the completed training.

Short evaluation activities during the training can be, for example, placing post-its to map the general satisfaction (if necessary with additional written explanations), a short description by each participant after selected sessions of two to three sentences of what they liked, what was learned or what was experienced as a problem, and a final round at the end of the day in which each participant briefly reports what they liked about the course,

what was missing and what they could use in their everyday work.

Another option for evaluation is to hand out written questionnaires to the participants or design surveys that can be conducted online. The focus can be on diverse aspects such as organisation and time management, topics, outcomes, level of involvement of participants, the possibility of expressing criticism or doubts or other aspects. One section of the questionnaire should collect socio-economic data, such as age, gender, occupation, etc. Filling out a questionnaire should not take more than 10 to 15 minutes. Written questionnaires can include open questions so participants can elaborate on their selected answers in comments. Since open questions are often reluctantly answered by participants, they should be kept to a minimum. Instead, it is recommended to collect final comments in a feedback-round at the end of the training.

[Appendix 7.4](#) presents examples of a [pre-training questionnaire](#), [post-training questionnaire](#) and an optional [survey on the retention of training content](#); these can be used for training sessions based on materials from the IMPROVE training platform. The questionnaires can be downloaded as Word documents from our training platform and adapted to one's own needs. The [survey on the retention of training content](#) is usually ideally done 3-6 months after training. However, from experience it has been found that the response rate is rather low (less than 15-20%) and that the work involved may not justify the outcome.

6. Other training handbooks

All sectors:

- **Friends and Family Handbook:** This is a handbook for friends, family members, neighbours, and colleagues of victims/survivors of domestic violence. The Friends and Family Handbook provides practical support and information for anyone worried about someone in their lives: <https://www.womensaid.org.uk/information-support/friends-and-family/>

Medical sector:

- **Pedagogic handbook tailored to the medical sector:** [VIPROM training handbook: https://viprom-cerv.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/VIPROM_TTT-Handbook-English.pdf](https://viprom-cerv.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/VIPROM_TTT-Handbook-English.pdf)
- **ICC VIPROM Handbook:** Intercultural Competence for Domestic Violence Trainers: A practical handbook developed as part of the VIPROM Project. Enhance your training approach with insights on intercultural sensitivity and inclusive practices. **Download the handbook here:** <https://eplus.uni-salzburg.at/obvusboa/download/pdf/11689053>

7. Appendices

Appendix 7.1 How to create a safe environment for trainings

These following group rules are designed to create a safe, respectful and effective learning environment when addressing the highly sensitive topic of domestic violence. Trainers can select the one that appear most relevant for their specific training context and adapt them to the specific group or make it a group decision to vote, which rules are the most important ones the group wishes to commit to.

➤ **Confidentiality is essential and non-negotiable.**

What is shared in the group stays in the group. This is crucial to ensure trust and openness.

➤ **Listen actively and acknowledging the perspectives of others.**

Pay attention without interrupting, use non-verbal cues to show understanding, and reflect back what you have heard when appropriate.

➤ **Respect diverse perspectives and experiences.**

Acknowledge that each participant may come from a different background and have different views shaped by their experiences.

➤ **Be mindful of triggers.**

*The content you will be sharing may be emotionally challenging on others. If you expect this to be the case, summarize briefly first what you are about to share to allow others to decide whether the content needs and should be shared. Self-care in cases of domestic violence is very importance. The **self-learning Module 9** on the training platform provides you with information on that ([police](#), [health](#), [social](#) and [legal](#) sectors)*

➤ **Avoid judgmental language.**

Use neutral and respectful words when talking about sensitive topics, even when you disagree.

➤ **Avoid generalization.**

Use “I” statements – speak from your personal experience rather than making generalisations about others.

➤ **Allow everyone the space to speak.**

Give each person the opportunity to share their thoughts, and avoid dominating the conversation.

➤ **Maintain a professional focus.**

Keep discussions relevant to the training content.

➤ **Respect time limits during discussions.**

Stay within the allocated time so that everyone has a chance to contribute.

➤ **Support a collaborative and respectful atmosphere.**

Encourage each other, share resources, and approach discussions with a spirit of teamwork.

➤ **Be mindful of the potential emotional impact the topics may have on you personally.**

Pauses are allowed. If you need to step out for a moment, feel free to do so quietly and return when ready.

➤ **Signal when a break is needed.**

Signal when a pause supports your learning process.

➤ **Commit to punctuality.**

Return from breaks on time to support the group's rhythm.

➤ **Use mobile devices only when relevant to the training.**

Keep phones on silent and ideally out of your focus area completely.

Appendix 7.2 Advantages, applications and requirements of various training methods

This Appendix summarises advantages, applications and requirements of the various training methods that can be used for domestic violence trainings. [The document can be download from the training platform](#) as well, it is the same for all sectors.

Training method	Advantages	Applications	Requirements
Brainstorming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>creative and stimulating way to get different points of view on a certain topic</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>participants are asked to contribute their associations and answers to a certain question or concept</i> • <i>initially only written down by the trainer without discussing them</i> • <i>following the collection process, the group begins to jointly analyse, structure, and discuss what has been collected</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>depending on the question or problem, five to ten minutes may already be sufficient</i> • <i>document solutions, p. e. on moderation cards or flipchart, to support the discussion</i>
Discussions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>key method of interactive and participatory learning</i> • <i>create the possibility to include a variety of perspectives, experiences, and strategies</i> • <i>increase the practical relevance of the training</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>questions are designed for both self-study and group work</i> • <i>before the training, the questions should be reviewed</i> • <i>decide whether questions need to be adapted or added to achieve the intended learning process with the specific target group</i> • <i>think about the possible answers of the participants beforehand in order to include the important points to be discussed in the training (even if they</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>plan enough time for reflection</i> • <i>trainer needs to be flexible and respond to topics and information that he or she is not prepared for</i>

		<i>do not come up in the discussion)</i>	
Group work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>can help to actively engage more participants</i> • <i>gives space to those who do not like to speak in larger groups</i> • <i>learner contributions, such as presentations, posters, and discussions, provide opportunities for active participation and help to reinforce learning</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>depending on the participants and the topics worked on, the groups can work either alone or be supported by the trainer</i> • <i>groups can be asked to appoint a spokesperson who will present the results of the group work afterwards</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>role of the trainer is then to make sure that the time is not exceeded</i> • <i>help with any questions or problems</i>
Case studies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>combine two methods: the case analysis itself and the discussion about it</i> • <i>promote critical thinking and problem-solving skills</i> • <i>enable to make decisions or assessments and develop solutions based on the information available</i> • <i>help participants transfer new information into practice</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>participants can elaborate specific questions to get more information</i> • <i>participants can identify key decisions or assessments that need to be made</i> • <i>case studies can also be used in group work or role play</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>effective cases are usually based on realistic scenarios</i> • <i>present complex, unstructured problems that may contain trivial or irrelevant information</i> • <i>often do not contain all the information a practitioner would need</i>
Role play	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>active learning method</i> • <i>allows participants to explore realistic situations by interacting with other participants</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>participants can be given specific instructions on how to behave or what to say</i> • <i>participants can be asked to act and</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>a safe environment that enables participants to own their role</i> • <i>Role plays need time (at</i>

	<p><i>in a safe environment</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>opportunity to learn and perceive situations from other perspectives</i> • <i>can be used to develop professional skills and to transfer learnings into practice</i> 	<p><i>react in their own way, depending on the exercise requirements</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>play the other side of a conversation or interaction</i> • <i>following the role play, participants are asked to reflect and discuss the interactions (e.g., alternative ways of dealing with the situation)</i> • <i>if necessary, the role play can be performed again, with changes made based on the results of the reflection and discussions</i> 	<p><i>least 20-30 minutes) and this needs to be planned in when designing the course agenda.</i></p>
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Appendix 7.3 Generic example of a role play on intersectoral collaboration

A [Word document](#) and a corresponding [PDF file](#) of that role play can be downloaded from our training platform; it is the same for all sectors. This role play can therefore easily be adapted to suit your needs, since the roles should be tailored to the judicial system of each country.

Objectives:

To practice trauma-informed, collaborative responses when a survivor is hesitant to testify in a legal process, especially for obtaining a restraining order. Participants will explore professional responsibilities, survivor autonomy, and cross-sector support.

Duration:

- Role play: 15–20 minutes
- Debrief: 20–30 minutes

PARTICIPANTS (4 Roles):

1. Survivor – "Leila"
2. Legal Advocate / Court-Based Social Worker
3. Police Domestic Violence Liaison Officer
4. Prosecutor / Legal Aid Attorney

SCENARIO OVERVIEW

Leila, 31, has endured years of psychological abuse, occasional physical violence, and stalking from her ex-partner, who recently showed up outside her workplace and home again. She has filed police reports, and the domestic violence liaison officer encouraged her to seek a restraining order. She meets with a legal advocate and a legal aid prosecutor to begin the process. However, once informed that she may need to testify in court, Leila becomes fearful. She worries about retaliation, losing custody of her kids, and not being believed. She begins expressing doubts and considers withdrawing the request.

ROLE DESCRIPTIONS

Leila (DV victim)

- Intelligent, cautious, overwhelmed.
- Has two young children.
- Has been emotionally manipulated to believe no one will help her.
- Terrified of court and retribution.
- Unsure if going through with the restraining order is worth the risk.
- Needs reassurance, safety planning, and control over decisions.

Legal Advocate / Court-Based Social Worker

- Trained in trauma-informed care.
- Your role is to support Leila emotionally and practically.
- You want to empower her, not pressure her.
- You know legal testimony is challenging, but you believe her safety depends on moving forward.
- You're trying to balance realism with hope.

Police DV Liaison Officer

- Familiar with Leila's case history.
- Believes the ex-partner poses a high risk of escalation.
- Wants to protect Leila but may speak in firm, procedural language.
- Has access to evidence like past incident reports, photos, text messages.
- Must not override Leila's autonomy, even if you disagree with her hesitation.

Prosecutor or Legal Aid Attorney

- Explains what's legally required to obtain the restraining order.
- Clarifies that testimony might be necessary, depending on the case strength.
- Balances legal limitations with victim-centred advocacy.
- You must explain realistic outcomes without discouraging Leila.

ROLE PLAY FLOW (Suggested Structure)

- ✓ Initial Scene (All participants in a joint meeting)
- ✓ Legal aid office or court preparation room.
- ✓ Leila expresses initial willingness but begins withdrawing.
- ✓ Escalation
- ✓ Leila hears she may have to testify and becomes emotional.
- ✓ She brings up fear of retaliation, loss of custody, and not being believed.
- ✓ Response from Others
- ✓ Advocate and police try to reassure her and support autonomy.
- ✓ Prosecutor explains her rights and options, including the possibility of protective testimony mechanisms (e.g., testifying via video; please note: this may differ between countries).
- ✓ Decision Point
- ✓ Leila must decide whether to continue or pause the restraining order process.
- ✓ Other actors must support either decision without coercion.

FACILITATOR PROMPTS

During or after the role play, ask:

- How did each professional balance support vs. pressure?
- Did anyone speak over Leila or make assumptions?
- What cross-sector communication helped or hindered trust?
- What barriers came up (legal, emotional, systemic)?
- What are non-testimonial options that can support her case?
- How can sectors collaborate to increase Leila's sense of safety and control?

NOTES FOR SAFETY

- Let participants "tap out" of the role if distressed.
- Offer grounding exercises or a short break if emotions run high.
- Remind participants that the goal is skill-building, not perfect performance.

FACILITATOR TIPS

- Use brief pre-briefs: provide each participant with a character summary.
- Debrief after each scenario with sector-specific and shared reflection.
- Rotate roles between sessions so participants see multiple perspectives.

Appendix 7.4 Evaluations of the training

Appendix 7.4.1 Pre-Training Questionnaire

A **Word document** of the pre-training questionnaire can be downloaded from our **training platform** and can therefore be easily adapted to suit your needs. This questionnaire is the same for all sectors.

To the participants:

Please take a few minutes to complete this questionnaire. Your reflections are highly valuable for you to get ready for the training, and they will help us design the training according to your expectations and knowledge. Your responses are anonymous.

Please take 10 minutes to improve the quality of the training! Thank you very much for your support!

1. Personal Code

Please create an **anonymous personal code** that allows us to match your responses across different stages without revealing your identity.

Note for trainers: *The personal code should be based on characteristics that are not identifiable by your organization/others you share the data with, but remain constant (e.g., 3rd letter in your mother's first name + month of birth + last digit of your postal code etc. + 1st letter in the name of your favourite colour etc.). Adapt this example to fit local legal and cultural requirements. Ensure it does not leave several options for answers.*

2. Demographic Information

Note for trainers: *Choose demographic questions to meet local data protection requirements and to collect only information essential for analysis. You find examples in the questionnaire that is suggested to be used directly after the training.*

3. Expectations, prior knowledge, challenges

1. Knowledge				
1.1 How would you rate your current level of knowledge on the topic of the upcoming training?				
<input type="checkbox"/> very confident	<input type="checkbox"/> confident	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> not confident	<input type="checkbox"/> not confident at all
<p>¹Note for trainers: <i>A more specific alternative would be picking up the objectives separately.</i></p> <p><i>Adjust items according to the training focus, e.g., to recognise indicators of domestic violence, to communicate with victims/survivors, to conduct risk assessments.</i></p>				
1.2 How would you rate your current ability to ...				
<input type="checkbox"/> very confident	<input type="checkbox"/> confident	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> not confident	<input type="checkbox"/> not confident at all

2. Expectations				
2.1 What is <u>one</u> specific question or challenge you hope this training will help you to address?				
2.2 What is <u>another</u> specific question or challenge you hope this training will help you to address?				
2.3 What are your expectations regarding the benefits of this training for your professional role?				
<input type="checkbox"/> very high	<input type="checkbox"/> high	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> low	<input type="checkbox"/> very low
3 Additional Feedback				
3.1 What are the two biggest obstacles you currently face in your professional role when addressing this topic?				
3.2 What is one aspect you already know about domestic violence that you think is most important for others to understand?				
3.3 Any comments or suggestions for this training?				

Thank you for your contribution!

It was a pleasure working with you in the training.

If you have any questions, please contact:

Appendix 7.4.2 Post-Evaluation of the training

A [Word document](#) of the post-training questionnaire can be downloaded from our training platform and can therefore be easily adapted to suit your needs. This questionnaire is the same for all sectors

To the participants:

After participating in the training, we would like to know if you are satisfied with the organisation and the content presented.

Please take 10 minutes to improve the quality of the training!

Thank you very much for your support!

1. Personal Code

Please create an **anonymous personal code** that allows us to match your responses across different stages without revealing your identity.

Note for trainers: *The personal code should be based on characteristics that are not identifiable by your organization/others you share the data with, but remain constant (e.g., 3rd letter in your mother's first name + month of birth + last digit of your postal code etc. + 1st letter in the name of your favourite colour etc.). Adapt this example to fit local legal and cultural requirements. Ensure it does not leave several options for answers.*

2. Demographic Information

Note for trainers: *Choose demographic questions to meet local data protection requirements and to collect only information essential for analysis. You find examples in the questionnaire that is suggested to be used in this template.*

3. Specific questions about content

1. Organisation of the training				
1.1 I found the information I received before the training ...				
<input type="checkbox"/> very useful	<input type="checkbox"/> useful	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> not very useful	<input type="checkbox"/> not useful at all
1.2 I found the organisation of the training ...				
<input type="checkbox"/> very good	<input type="checkbox"/> good	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> bad	<input type="checkbox"/> very bad
1.3 The duration and schedule of the training were ...				
<input type="checkbox"/> very good	<input type="checkbox"/> good	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> bad	<input type="checkbox"/> very bad
1.4 The composition of the group was ...				
<input type="checkbox"/> very good	<input type="checkbox"/> good	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> bad	<input type="checkbox"/> very bad
2. Content and methods				
2.1 The presentations (lectures by the trainers) in the training were ...				
<input type="checkbox"/> comprehensible	<input type="checkbox"/> largely comprehensible	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> largely incomprehensible	<input type="checkbox"/> incomprehensible

2.2 The support in training was ...				
<input type="checkbox"/> very useful	<input type="checkbox"/> useful	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> not very useful	<input type="checkbox"/> not useful at all
2.3 I found the discussion in the training ...				
<input type="checkbox"/> very interesting	<input type="checkbox"/> interesting	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> not very interesting	<input type="checkbox"/> not interesting at all
2.4 I found the methods used in the training ...				
<input type="checkbox"/> very effective	<input type="checkbox"/> effective	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> not very effective	<input type="checkbox"/> not effective at all
2.5 The quality of the learning materials in the training was ...				
<input type="checkbox"/> very high	<input type="checkbox"/> high	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> low	<input type="checkbox"/> very low
2.6 Too much time was spent on:				
2.7 Too little time was spent on:				
2.8 In the training I missed:				
3. Learning outcomes				
3.1 The training increased my awareness of the phenomenon of domestic violence.				
<input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree	<input type="checkbox"/> agree	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> strongly disagree
3.2 The training improved my ability to help victims of domestic violence.				
<input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree	<input type="checkbox"/> agree	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> strongly disagree
3.3 The training encouraged me to reflect on my own views and possible prejudices on domestic violence.				
<input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree	<input type="checkbox"/> agree	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> strongly disagree
3.4 The learning content of the training for my (future) work is ...				
<input type="checkbox"/> very useful	<input type="checkbox"/> useful	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> not very useful	<input type="checkbox"/> not useful at all
4. Evaluation of own participation				
4.1 My opportunities to participate in the training were ...				

<input type="checkbox"/> completely sufficient	<input type="checkbox"/> sufficient	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> insufficient	<input type="checkbox"/> not sufficient at all
4.2 My opportunities to contribute my own expertise were ...				
<input type="checkbox"/> completely sufficient	<input type="checkbox"/> sufficient	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> insufficient	<input type="checkbox"/> not sufficient at all
4.3 My opportunities to bring in my doubts, uncertainties and critical remarks were ...				
<input type="checkbox"/> completely sufficient	<input type="checkbox"/> sufficient	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> insufficient	<input type="checkbox"/> not sufficient at all
5. General impression				
5.1 My general impression of the training is ...				
<input type="checkbox"/> very good	<input type="checkbox"/> good	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> bad	<input type="checkbox"/> very bad
5.2 Further comments:				
6. Personal and institutional background				
6.1 My reason for attending the training:				
6.2 Status of my institution:				
<input type="checkbox"/> governmental institution	<input type="checkbox"/> non-governmental institution	<input type="checkbox"/> private institution	<input type="checkbox"/> other status:	
6.3 Field of work (multiple answers possible):				
<input type="checkbox"/> law enforcement	<input type="checkbox"/> healthcare	<input type="checkbox"/> social work	<input type="checkbox"/> education	
6.4 Work experience with domestic violence (in years):				
<input type="checkbox"/> none	<input type="checkbox"/> 0-3 years	<input type="checkbox"/> 3-6 years	<input type="checkbox"/> more than 6 years	
6.5 Already received training on domestic violence				
<input type="checkbox"/> none	<input type="checkbox"/> for a few hours	<input type="checkbox"/> for a few days	<input type="checkbox"/> for a few weeks	
6.6 Occupational group (multiple answers possible):				
<input type="checkbox"/> management	<input type="checkbox"/> practitioner	<input type="checkbox"/> student	<input type="checkbox"/> other occupational group:	
6.7 Gender and age:				
<input type="checkbox"/> woman	<input type="checkbox"/> man	<input type="checkbox"/> non-binary	age:	

Thank you for your contribution!

It was a pleasure working with you in the training.

If you have any questions, please contact:

Appendix 7.4.3 Survey on retention of learning content (optional)

A [Word document](#) of this survey can be downloaded from our training platform and can therefore be easily adapted to suit your needs. This questionnaire is the same for all sectors

To the participants:

Thank you for taking the time to help us improve our training programme.

This short follow-up questionnaire will help us understand what knowledge, reflections, and practical skills have remained with your x months after the training, and whether you have had opportunities to apply them in your work. Your answers will be anonymous.

Please take 10 minutes to improve the quality of the training! Thank you very much for your support!

1. Personal Code

Please create an **anonymous personal code** that allows us to match your responses across different stages without revealing your identity.

***Note for trainers:** The personal code should be based on characteristics that are not identifiable by your organization/others you share the data with, but remain constant (e.g., 3rd letter in your mother’s first name + month of birth + last digit of your postal code etc. + 1st letter in the name of your favourite colour etc.). Adapt this example to fit local legal and cultural requirements. Ensure it does not leave several options for answers.*

2. Demographic Information

***Note for trainers:** Choose demographic questions to meet local data protection requirements and to collect only information essential for analysis. You find examples in the questionnaire that is suggested to be used directly after the training ([Annex 7.4.2](#))*

1. Opportunity to use my new skills and knowledge on Domestic Violence				
1.1 Since the training, I have had opportunities to apply what I learned in my work <i>(Note for trainers: Create the questionnaire in a way that, if the answer is “no”, Section 2 is skipped and the respondent is directed to Section 3).</i>				
<input type="checkbox"/> yes	<input type="checkbox"/> no			
2. Transfer to Practice [only for those who answered “yes” to Question 1.1]				
2.1 I have applied the knowledge and skills from the training in my professional role.				
<input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree	<input type="checkbox"/> agree	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> strongly disagree
2.2 I have used the training content to improve my ability to help victims of domestic violence.				
<input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree	<input type="checkbox"/> agree	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> strongly disagree
2.3 I have continued to reflect on my own views and possible prejudices regarding domestic violence				

<input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree	<input type="checkbox"/> agree	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> strongly disagree
2.4 The training content has influenced how I approach challenges in my work.				
<input type="checkbox"/> strongly agree	<input type="checkbox"/> agree	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> strongly disagree
2.5 The training content that has been most useful in my work is				
2.6 The biggest obstacle to applying what I learned has been:				
3. Retention of learning				
3.1 The most important insight or concept I still remember from the training is:				
3.2 Since the training, my awareness of the phenomenon of domestic violence is:				
<input type="checkbox"/> higher	<input type="checkbox"/> about the same	<input type="checkbox"/> lower		
3.3 Since the training, my ability to support victims of domestic violence is:				
<input type="checkbox"/> higher	<input type="checkbox"/> about the same	<input type="checkbox"/> lower		
3.4 I have new questions or topics that I would like to explore further:				
3.5 My overall view of the training, now that some time has passed, is				
<input type="checkbox"/> very good	<input type="checkbox"/> good	<input type="checkbox"/> neutral	<input type="checkbox"/> bad	<input type="checkbox"/> very bad
3.6 Additional comments				

Thank you for your contribution!

We look forward to working with you in the training.

If you have any questions, please contact:

Appendix 7.5 Domestic Violence Training Preparation Checklist

A [Word document](#) of this checklist can be downloaded from our training platform.

Category	Checklist Item	Completed
Trainer Preparation	Familiarised with teaching materials and content	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Prepared personal notes if needed	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Allocated sufficient preparation time	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Trigger warnings planned	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Trainer team briefed on escalation procedures	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Contact list of relevant support organisations ready	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Welcome E-Mail sent out to participants (including pre-survey)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Equipment & Materials	Additional resources (images, videos) prepared	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>On-the-day</i>	Laptop, projector, and internet connection checked	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Whiteboard, paper board, and markers available	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Stationery (adhesives, pens, coloured cardboard, fasteners) ready	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Furniture arranged for course (e.g., semicircle or Π)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Training Area	Adequate space for group work and role-play; (e.g., 35 m ² for 12 trainees)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Work duties covered during absence	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Timing suitable (not during lunch, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Set-up requirements listed (and assigned to someone, if possible)	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>On-the-day</i>	Arrive 1 hour early for set-up	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Test equipment functionality	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Materials organised and ready to use	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Support resources (helpline numbers, handouts) placed visibly	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Evaluation form/link prepared	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Venue technical support contact obtained	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lighting and temperature checked	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Break and lunch arrangements confirmed	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Quiet room or space for overwhelmed participants organized	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Restroom facilities located and checked	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Greet and welcome participants on arrival	<input type="checkbox"/>